

Formulation and Nutritional Assessment of Antioxidant-Enriched Chocolate Energy Bites

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the Formulation and Standardization of Functional Chocolate Energy bites enriched with natural antioxidants and magnesium. The product was developed using Flax seeds, Chia seeds, Walnuts, Almonds, Pistachios, Dates and Dark Chocolate-ingredients selected for their high nutrient density and functional properties. Three formulations (T₁, T₂, T₃) were prepared by varying the ingredient ratios and evaluated for sensory quality using a 7-point hedonic scale. Comprehensive nutritional profiling included proximate analysis, mineral composition, antioxidant potential (via DPPH, ABTS, FRAP assays) and essential fatty acid content determined by gas chromatography. Microbial analysis was conducted over a 30-day refrigerated storage period. Among the samples, T₃ demonstrated the highest overall acceptability, superior antioxidant capacity (ABTS: 1047 mg/100 g) and excellent microbial stability (TPC <10 CFU/g). The results confirm that the developed formulation serves as a health-promoting, shelf-stable snack with potential applications in functional food product development.

Keywords: Functional foods, Antioxidant capacity, Chocolate energy bites and Nutrient analysis

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing demand for functional food products that offer health-promoting properties beyond basic nutrition. This trend is driven largely by increasing awareness of the role of diet in the prevention and management of lifestyle-related diseases such as cardiovascular disorders, obesity and type 2 diabetes. Consumers are progressively seeking convenient, nutrient-dense snack options that provide natural sources of energy and essential micronutrients while minimizing the intake of refined sugars and synthetic additives (Martirosyan & Singh, 2015) [14]. On this basis, energy bites composed of nuts, seeds, fruits and dark chocolate represent a promising category of Functional Foods due to their rich composition in Bioactive Compounds.

Flax seeds (*Linum usitatissimum*) are an excellent source of α -linolenic acid, dietary fiber and lignans; all of which contribute to their well-documented antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects (Goyal *et al.*, 2014) [9]. Chia seeds (*Salvia hispanica* L.) provide a complementary nutrient profile, particularly high in omega-3 fatty acids, calcium and polyphenols (Ullah *et al.*, 2016) [22]. Nuts such as

almonds, pistachios and walnuts contribute essential fatty acids, vitamin E, plant-based protein and flavonoids; Nuts have been associated with improved lipid profiles and reduced oxidative stress (Ros, 2010) [17]. Dates offer natural sweetness, dietary fiber and phenolic antioxidants which enhance flavor and functional value without the need for added sugars (Al-Farsi & Lee, 2008) [2]. Dark chocolate known for its high flavonoid content, particularly epicatechin and catechin; which supports endothelial function and exhibits potent antioxidant capacity (Katz *et al.*, 2011) [13].

While individual components of these ingredients have been studied extensively, there remains a gap in the literature concerning the combined effects of such nutrient-dense formulations, particularly when standardized into a functional, ready-to-consume form like energy bites. Furthermore, scientific evaluation of the antioxidant activity, mineral content, microbial stability and sensory properties of these formulations is crucial for their commercial Demand and Nutritional validation. This study aims to address this gap by formulating and standardizing chocolate-based energy bites using antioxidant-rich,

magnesium-enhanced ingredients. The formulation is evaluated for its nutritional profile, antioxidant potential, microbial safety and consumer acceptability under refrigerated storage conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Ingredient Procurement

All ingredients used in the preparation of the chocolate energy bites were procured from certified local organic vendors in Hyderabad, Telangana, India. The selected ingredients included flax seeds, chia seeds, walnuts, almonds, pistachios, seedless dates, and dark chocolate with a cocoa content of 70%. All raw materials were stored under appropriate conditions to maintain quality and prevent oxidative degradation prior to product development.

2.2 Preparation of the Product

Nuts (walnuts, almonds, pistachios) and seeds (flax, chia) were dry-roasted individually at 120 °C for 2 minutes to enhance flavor and reduce moisture content, following the method adapted from Ros (2010) [17]. Roasted ingredients were then cooled and coarsely ground using a food processor. Dates were deseeded, chopped, and blended to form a natural binding paste. Dark chocolate was melted at 45 °C over a double boiler to retain its polyphenolic content (Katz *et al.*, 2011) [13]. The prepared components were mixed thoroughly to form a homogenous dough-like consistency. The mixture was then portioned into silicone molds, compressed to remove air pockets, and refrigerated at 4 °C for 1 hour to set. After demolding, the energy bites were stored in airtight containers under refrigeration (4–6 °C) for subsequent analysis.

2.3 Formulation of T₁, T₂ and T₃ Chocolate Energy Bites: Three formulations were developed by varying the proportion of nuts, dates, and dark chocolate, while keeping the flax and chia seed content constant across all samples (Table 1). The goal was to optimize sensory, nutritional, and functional characteristics.

Table 1: Composition of T₁, T₂ and T₃ Chocolate Energy Bites

Ingredients	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Flax seeds	20 g	20 g	20 g
Chia seeds	20 g	20 g	20 g
Walnuts	60 g	40 g	40 g
Pistachios	30 g	30 g	30 g
Almonds	60 g	40 g	40 g
Dates	170 g	150 g	160 g
Dark chocolate	95 g	100 g	90 g

2.4 Sensory Evaluation of Chocolate Energy Bites

Sensory characteristics were evaluated by a panel of 20 semi-trained participants aged between 22 and 45 years. The panel was selected based on interest and availability, and trained in basic sensory analysis protocols following Meilgaard *et al.* (2007) [15]. Each formulation was coded with a random three-digit number and served at room temperature. A 7-point hedonic scale was used to assess appearance, taste, texture, aroma, and overall acceptability, where 1 indicated “dislike very much” and 7 indicated “like very much.” Samples were presented in randomized order to minimize bias.

Fig 1: Preparation of T₁, T₂ and T₃ Samples

2.5 Nutritional Analysis of Chocolate Energy Bites

Proximate composition—moisture, crude protein, total fat, ash, crude fiber, and carbohydrates (by difference)—was determined using standard procedures outlined by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 2016) [3]. Moisture content was measured by oven drying at 105 °C, protein by the Kjeldahl method (N × 6.25), fat by Soxhlet extraction, ash content by muffle furnace at 550 °C, and fiber by enzymatic–gravimetric method.

2.6 Mineral and Vitamin Analysis of Chocolate Energy Bites

Magnesium, iron, calcium, and potassium (AOAC, 2016) [3]. Vitamin A by (AOAC 2001.13) and Vitamin D by (AOAC 2012.10), while vitamin C was analyzed spectrophotometrically using 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol as a titrant (Skoog *et al.*, 2017) [19].

2.7 Antioxidant Analysis of Chocolate Energy Bites

Antioxidant activity was determined through three in vitro assays:

- **DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay:** Based on the method by Brand-Williams *et al.* (1995) [6], with absorbance measured at 517 nm.
- **ABTS Radical Cation Decolorization Assay:** Conducted using the protocol by Re *et al.* (1999) [16], with results expressed in Trolox equivalents.
- **FRAP Assay (Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power):** Conducted according to Benzie and Strain (1996) [5], measuring the ability to reduce Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺.

Total polyphenol content was measured using the Folin–Ciocalteu reagent, and flavonoids were quantified with aluminum chloride colorimetric assay.

2.8 Microbial Analysis of Chocolate Energy Bites

Microbial quality of the samples was assessed at 0, 7, 14, 21, and 30 days of refrigerated storage (4 °C). Total Plate Count (TPC), Yeast and Mold Count, Coliforms, *Escherichia coli*, and *Salmonella* were evaluated according to the methods described in the Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI, 2020) [8] manual and ISO 4833-1:2013 standards.

Samples (25 g) were homogenized in sterile buffered peptone water and serially diluted. TPC was determined on Plate Count Agar, yeast and mold on Potato Dextrose Agar, and coliforms on MacConkey Agar. *E. coli* and *Salmonella* were detected using selective enrichment and biochemical confirmation.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Sensory Evaluation of T₁, T₂ and T₃ Chocolate Energy Bites

Based on the sensory evaluation results presented in Table 2, formulation T₃ demonstrated the highest scores across all attributes-appearance (6.6 ± 0.3), texture (6.5 ± 0.3), taste (6.6 ± 0.2), aroma (6.4 ± 0.3), and overall acceptability (6.5 ± 0.3)-indicating a significantly better acceptance compared to T₁ and T₂ ($p < 0.05$). The enhanced preference for T₃ can be attributed to its balanced composition of dates and dark chocolate, which offered a desirable natural sweetness, smooth texture, and rich flavor profile. The inclusion of nuts and seeds added a favorable mouthfeel without overpowering the taste. These findings align with Abbasi *et al.* (2020) [1], who reported improved sensory scores in date-based chocolate truffles with moderated dark chocolate content, and with Ismail *et al.* (2013) [11], who observed better palatability in chocolate-nut bars complemented by moist dried fruits. Overall, T₃ sample superior sensory performance highlights its potential as a consumer-preferred, functional snack option combining nutritional value with sensory appeal. T₃ sample was selected for further Nutrient and Microbial analysis.

Table 2: Sensory Evaluation Scores (Mean \pm SD) of Chocolate Energy Bite

Sensory Attribute	T ₁ (Mean \pm SD)	T ₂ (Mean \pm SD)	T ₃ (Mean \pm SD)
Appearance	5.84 \pm 0.4	6.02 \pm 0.5	6.60 \pm 0.3
Texture	5.62 \pm 0.5	6.14 \pm 0.4	6.52 \pm 0.3
Taste	5.70 \pm 0.6	6.02 \pm 0.4	6.64 \pm 0.2
Aroma	5.54 \pm 0.4	6.05 \pm 0.5	6.42 \pm 0.3
Overall Acceptability	5.80 \pm 0.5	6.15 \pm 0.4	6.50 \pm 0.3

3.2 Nutritional Composition of Chocolate Energy Bites (T₃)

The proximate composition of Chocolate Energy Bites T₃ per 100 g was as follows: energy 443.5 kcal, protein 13.01 g, fat 20.3 g, carbohydrates 52.19 g, fiber 7.1 g, moisture 7.0% and ash 0.45 g. The relatively high energy density and macronutrient balance make it suitable as a functional snack for both general and physically active populations. The fiber content is notable, offering over 25% of the recommended daily intake for adults, which can support satiety and digestive health (Slavin, 2013) [20]. In comparison, Ukeyima *et al.* (2018) [21] reported a similar fat and protein profile in functional snack bars made with dried fruit and nut combinations, though our product had a slightly higher fiber content due to the inclusion of chia and flax seeds.

Table 3: Nutritional Composition of Chocolate Energy Bites (T₃)

Nutrient	Amount
Energy (kcal)	443.5
Protein (g)	13.01
Carbohydrates(g)	52.19
Fat(g)	20.3
Dietary fiber(g)	7.1
Moisture (%)	7.0
Ash (g)	0.45

3.3 Mineral and Vitamin Content of Chocolate Energy Bites:

The mineral and vitamin content of Chocolate Energy

Bites T₃ demonstrated appreciable levels of key minerals per 100 g: magnesium (59.05 mg), potassium (213 mg), iron (1.9 mg), and calcium (23.7 mg). These values indicate the product's potential to contribute to daily micronutrient requirements, especially magnesium, which plays a vital role in neuromuscular function and energy metabolism (Volpe, 2013) [23]. When compared to commercial chocolate-based snack products, which typically contain 30–40 mg of magnesium per 100 g, our formulation shows an enhanced mineral profile, largely due to the integration of flax, chia seeds, and almonds (Ros, 2010) [17]. Additionally, the inclusion of dark chocolate, known for its magnesium and polyphenol content, further supports the functional nutritional profile (Katz *et al.*, 2011) [13].

Table 4: Mineral and Vitamin Content Per 100g

Parameter	Amount (mg)
Iron	1.9
calcium	23.7
magnesium	59.05
potassium	213
Vitamin A	10.5
Vitamin C	0.6
Vitamin D	0.1

3.4 Antioxidant Capacity of Chocolate Energy Bites

T₃ exhibited strong antioxidant activity across all three assays: DPPH (319 mg TE/100 g), FRAP (576 mg TE/100 g) and ABTS (1047 mg TE/100 g). Additionally, total flavonoids and polyphenols were measured at 279 mg/100 g and 516 mg/100 g, respectively (Table 5). The high ABTS value indicates potent radical scavenging capacity, attributable to the synergistic effect of dark chocolate, dates, and polyphenol-rich nuts. Our findings align with those of Cooper *et al.* (2008) [7], who reported DPPH values ranging between 250–350 mg TE/100 g for dark chocolate (70% cocoa) and Helal *et al.* (2018) [10], who demonstrated that incorporating dates and nuts significantly enhanced antioxidant capacity in confectionery items. Notably, our use of minimal thermal processing (below 50 °C for chocolate melting) preserved the integrity of antioxidant compounds, as recommended by Basu *et al.* (2011) [4].

Table 5: Antioxidant capacity (mg TE/100g)

Antioxidant type	value
DPPH	319
FRAP	576
ABTS	1047
Flavonoids	279
polyphenols	516

3.5 Microbial Stability of Chocolate Energy Bites

Microbial analysis of the T₃ formulation over a 30-day refrigerated storage period confirmed its safety and shelf stability. The Total Plate Count (TPC) remained < 10 CFU/g and no yeast, mold, coliforms, *E. coli*, or *Salmonella* were detected throughout the storage period. These results comply with international safety standards for ready-to-eat snack products (ISO 4833-1:2013; FSSAI, 2020) [8]. The low water activity of the product, combined with the antimicrobial properties of ingredients like dates and dark chocolate (which contain polyphenolic compounds), likely

contributed to microbial inhibition. A similar microbial profile was observed by Sharma *et al.* (2019) ^[18] in the development of protein-rich snack bars stored under refrigeration.

Table 6: Microbial Analysis

Microbial parameter	Result	Limit
Total viable count	<10CFU/g	1x 10 ⁶
Yeast & mold count	<10 CFU/g	1x 10 ⁶
<i>E. coli</i>	Absent	Absent/25g
Salmonella	Absent	Absent/25g
Coliforms	Absent	Absent/25g

4. Conclusion

The present study successfully developed and standardized antioxidant-rich chocolate energy bites using a combination of nutrient-dense ingredients including flax seeds, chia seeds, nuts, dates, and dark chocolate. Among the three formulations, T₃ demonstrated the highest sensory acceptability, a balanced macronutrient and micronutrient profile and superior antioxidant potential. Its magnesium, polyphenol, and flavonoid content contribute to functional health benefits, particularly for cardiovascular and neuromuscular support. Furthermore, the product maintained excellent microbial stability over 30 days of refrigerated storage, confirming its shelf suitability. Overall, the T₃ formulation offers a promising, wholesome alternative to conventional snacks, aligning well with current consumer demand for natural, functional and health-oriented foods.

5. References

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